

EIJASTR

EUROPEAN INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF APPLIED SCIENCES AND THEORETICAL RESEARCH

International Scientific Journal

2026

European International Journal Of Applied Sciences And Theoretical Research

Volume 02, Issue 05

EDITORIAL BOARD:**Professor Emma Franke**

Editor in Chief

Prof. Jo Coldwell-Neilson

Associate Editor In Chief Deakin University, Australia

Mr Mohd Helmy

Abd Wahab Universiti Tun Hussein Onn Malaysia, Malaysia

Shafi'i Muhammad Abdulhamid

Federal University Of Technology Minna, Nigeria., Nigeria

Dr Man Fung (Kelvin) Lo

The Chinese University Of Hong Kong, Hong Kong

Dr Ahmad Samed

Al-Adwan Al Ahliyya Amman University, Jordan

Waleed Alsabhan

Kacst, Saudi Arabia Yvonne Antonucci Widener University, United States

Prof. Orit Avidov Ungar

Achva Academic College & Open University Of Israel, Israel

Dr. Aslina Baharum

Universiti Malaysia Sabah, Malaysia

THE PARTICIPATION OF “UZSELKHOZTEKHNIKA” IN THE SYSTEM OF TRAINING PERSONNEL FOR AGRICULTURE

Sanjarbek Toyirov Saydali oqli

Independent Researcher of Fergana State University

Abstract: This article analyzes the role and participation of “Uzselkhoztekhnika” in the system of training personnel for the agricultural sector during the Soviet period in Uzbekistan. The study examines the processes of preparing mechanized workers, tractor drivers, engineers, and technical specialists necessary for the development of agriculture under the conditions of collectivization and large-scale mechanization. Special attention is paid to the activities of “Uzselkhoztekhnika” in organizing training courses, improving the qualifications of agricultural workers, and providing practical education through technical bases and production facilities.

Keywords: Uzselkhoztekhnika, agriculture, personnel training, mechanization, tractor drivers, agricultural specialists, Soviet agriculture, vocational education, cotton harvesting machines, agricultural reforms, technical personnel, Uzbekistan, machine-tractor fleet, vocational schools, agricultural modernization.

Introduction. The further strengthening of the Soviet administrative-command system in the national economy led to the widespread expansion of falsification, theft, and bribery within economic sectors, resulting in the moral degradation and corruption of a certain segment of personnel. In particular, after the abolition of private property and the transfer of all enterprises, land, and harvests into state ownership, the growing demand for agricultural products during the periods of collectivization and industrialization necessitated the training of specialists for the agricultural sector.

Literature Review and Methodology. The topic of the participation of “Uzselkhoztekhnika” in the system of training personnel for agriculture is closely connected with the modernization of Uzbekistan’s agricultural sector, the provision of technical equipment, and the preparation of qualified specialists. Scientific literature on this subject mainly addresses agrarian reforms, technical service systems, agricultural mechanization, and the training of professional personnel.

Archival documents, statistical data, and periodical press materials related to the topic provide an opportunity to scientifically study the role of “Uzselkhoztekhnika” in eliminating the shortage of technical personnel in agriculture, developing practice-oriented education, and training mechanized workers. At the

same time, comprehensive historical studies devoted specifically to this issue remain relatively limited, demonstrating the necessity for further in-depth research in this field.

In conducting this research, historical, objective, systematic, and comparative analytical methods were employed. During the research process, legislative documents of the Republic of Uzbekistan, archival materials, statistical data, scientific literature, and periodical publications were analyzed. Furthermore, the participation of the “Uzselkhoztekhnika” system in training agricultural personnel was examined through historical stages, while institutional changes and practical outcomes in the sector were highlighted through comparative analysis.

Results and Discussion. By 1950, more than 100 agricultural institutes and technical schools had been established throughout the Soviet Union, with over 200,000 students studying there. Beginning in the 1950s, administrative interference at all levels—from the Union center to district administrations—transformed agriculture into a sector that merely fulfilled party directives, denying free market relations. At that time, almost no one realized that these policies would eventually contribute to the decline of the national economy.

Grandiloquent speeches, reports, and official documents constantly emphasized the issue of training personnel for agriculture. For this purpose, specialized agricultural technical schools, higher educational institutions, and advanced training courses were established. Correspondence departments were opened in agricultural technical schools, primarily aimed at improving the qualifications of middle-level agricultural personnel such as brigade leaders, unit heads, department chiefs, farm managers, and accountants.

A number of resolutions were adopted to organize the provision of qualified personnel for the country’s agriculture and to establish a system of distance education. Nevertheless, the problem of supplying villages with mechanized personnel persisted. Many machine operators in rural areas lacked proper training, and in some cases there were not even qualified operators to work on “KhT-1.2” cotton-picking machines.

In order to provide economic education for agricultural personnel and to organize the operation of machinery in two shifts, collective and state farm workers were trained at the “Tashselmash” завод and at the training bases of “Uzselkhoztekhnika.” However, these measures were temporary and insufficient to fully address the shortage of personnel.

The expansion of newly cultivated lands and the continuous increase in the number of tractors and machinery led to a constant rise in demand for qualified specialists. However, the number of machine-tractors delivered to the agricultural sector greatly exceeded the number of trained specialists. For example, in 1965 nearly 1,000 students graduated from vocational and technical schools in the Syrdarya region, while by 1970 this number had reached 1,500.

In 1965 alone, collective farms of the Syrdarya region purchased 2,646 tractors, 1,144 cotton-picking machines, and 129 combines from the state. During the same year, state farms in the region received 5,970 tractors, 1,819 cotton-picking machines, and 593 combines. This clearly demonstrated the serious imbalance between the replenishment of machine-tractor fleets with technical equipment and the supply of mechanized personnel.

According to data from the Syrdarya region in 1965, the total number of machine operators, combine drivers, bulldozer operators, and other technical personnel was around 10,000. However, the Mirzachul zone alone required an additional 2,000 machine operators. As a result, due to the shortage of mechanized personnel, newly delivered machinery in some machine-tractor fleets remained idle for long periods, leading to a decline in economic efficiency.

During preparations for the 1963 cotton harvest, the Central Committee of the Communist Party of Uzbekistan and the Council of Ministers of the Uzbek SSR noted delays in harvest preparations by the departments of “Uzselkhoztekhnika,” procurement centers, cotton-processing plants, and local party and Soviet bodies. Consequently, it was decided that within two weeks mechanical drivers should be selected and trained at courses organized under the republican branches of “Uzselkhoztekhnika” and at state farms to ensure the operation of cotton-picking machines in two shifts. Across the republic, 5,000 mechanical drivers were to be trained and 10,000 retrained.

At the March Plenum of the CPSU Central Committee in 1965, special attention was given to training engineering and technical personnel, tractor drivers, combine operators, and other mechanized workers for agriculture, as well as ensuring their material interest in increasing production, improving the use of machinery, and preserving equipment.

In 1966, the CPSU Central Committee adopted the resolution “On Improving Higher and Secondary Specialized Education for Better Personnel Training in the Country.” Following this, the Central Committee of the Communist Party of Uzbekistan and the Council of Ministers of the Uzbek SSR adopted resolutions in 1966 “On Further Improving the Effectiveness of the System for Advanced Training of Agricultural Specialists and Managers of Collective and State Farms,” in November 1967 “On Improving the Training of Scientific and Scientific-Pedagogical Personnel,” and in August 1969 “On Establishing Preparatory Departments under Higher Educational Institutions.” These resolutions defined tasks related to training personnel capable of supporting the national economy and agriculture.

Within the “Uzselkhoztekhnika” associations themselves, although the 1965 plan required 6,712 mechanical drivers, only 3,134 mechanized personnel were trained. Mechanical drivers were prepared in Andijan, Kurgantepa, Isboskan, and Namangan districts. Shortages of housing, the absence of kindergartens, inadequate repair workshops, and poor social conditions caused a high turnover of personnel.

In most cases, higher authorities merely demanded that district branches of “Uzselkhoztekhnika” intensify repair work on cotton-picking machinery without resolving underlying social problems.

From March 30 to April 9, 1971, the XXIV Congress of the CPSU Central Committee was held. In accordance with its decisions, Uzbekistan planned to train 247,100 workers through the vocational-technical education system between 1971 and 1975. The number of vocational schools in the republic was to increase to 266, including the establishment of 135 new vocational schools and 85 secondary vocational schools providing both vocational and general secondary education.

However, these reforms were implemented alongside numerous shortcomings and problems. During this period, more than 30,000 specialists were trained in the republic, and between 1971 and 1973, 18,209 specialists graduated through correspondence education. Nevertheless, many of the trained personnel were inadequately prepared for agricultural work. Although they were expected to become masters of their profession, insufficient professional skills were interpreted as a lack of “communist morality, high culture, and conscientious attitudes toward labor and study.”

On August 15, 1973, the Central Committee of the Communist Party of Uzbekistan adopted a resolution “On the Implementation of Party and Government Decisions to Eliminate Mismanagement and Theft of Socialist Property in the ‘Uzselkhoztekhnika’ Association.” Cases of embezzlement and misuse of state property within the association were attributed to the improper selection and placement of personnel.

At that time, 1,600 employees worked in the material-technical supply system of the association, most of whom lacked professional qualifications and could not adequately solve technical and organizational issues. Of the 1,660 chief accountants employed in affiliated organizations, only 146 possessed higher education diplomas, while 428 had incomplete higher or secondary education. Among 878 commodity specialists, only 16 had higher education degrees.

Between 1968 and 1973, the Institute for Advanced Training under the “Uzselkhoztekhnika” Association, higher educational institutions, and various courses trained 895 employees, including 162 directors and specialists of trade bases. Between 1970 and 1973, approximately 6,000 individuals received training.

Most trainees were young people who had completed only the 8th or 9th grade of secondary school. About 50,000 such youths were trained as mechanized workers in district association courses. In the Chinaz district of Tashkent region and several districts of Samarkand region, women were also extensively trained as turners and locksmiths.

Despite these efforts, due to the absence of permanent workers in the associations of the Karakalpak ASSR and Khorezm region, mechanized workers were often employed temporarily. Personnel turnover between 1970 and 1972 reached 19

percent. In 1972 alone, loss of working time due to various reasons amounted to 135,000 man-days.

At the same time, 26,000 workers employed in organizations subordinate to the association and 494 employees working in 38 workshops and sections were awarded various Soviet orders and medals.

Various slogans were also used to strengthen the training of mechanized workers. For example, at the Akhunboboev collective farm in the Urta Chirchik district of Tashkent region, economic training programs were introduced, and the slogan promoted by renowned mechanized worker and Hero of Socialist Labor Shoimardon Kudratov together with the Shodiev brothers — “If you live in the countryside, master the profession of mechanization” — was widely used.

For instance, in 1975, 218 mechanized personnel worked at the “Pakhtakor” state farm in Pakhtakor district of Jizzakh region. Every year, 30–35 mechanized workers were trained through courses. Nevertheless, during harvesting seasons, when cotton-picking machines, transport tractors, root-cutting and root-removing machines, and driving tractors operated simultaneously, shortages of 250–300 mechanized workers were still observed. At the same time, mechanized workers supervised 54 cotton-growing brigades.

Conclusion. In conclusion, it should be emphasized that numerous shortcomings were also evident in the training of mechanized personnel. In 1986, in many farms of the district agro-industrial association, 15.6 units of machinery corresponded to every 10 mechanized workers; that is, there were only 1,093 tractor drivers for 1,250 tractors and 450 cotton-picking machines.

During the year, tractors were used in fieldwork for only 154 days, and even then only in a single shift. Repair expenditures reached 1.696 million rubles, significantly exceeding planned figures. The shortage of mechanized personnel was mainly compensated for by graduates of two rural vocational schools and four- and eight-month training courses in the district.

In 1986, vocational schools trained 154 tractor drivers, while short-term courses prepared more than 280 additional operators. Although various decisions were adopted to improve the preservation and effective use of machinery and mechanisms in order to increase production efficiency, irresponsibility among mechanized workers and farm managers remained extremely high.

References

1. Zoyirov T., Dilmurodov A. Texnikaga munosabat shumi? // Sovet O‘zbekistoni. 1985 yil 19 may.
2. Yerjanov S., Bayjanov O. Yutuqlar mustahkamlanadi // O‘zbekiston qishloq xo‘jaligi. 1987. -№6, - 13 bet.
3. O‘zbekiston Kompartiyasi Markaziy Komitetida // Sovet O‘zbekistoni. 1978 yil 17 yanvar.
4. Qoriyev Sh., G‘ulomov K., Tursunov R. Vaqt kutib turmaydi // Sovet O‘zbekistoni. 1977 yil 9 avgust.